

ICUC Score

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Measuring the outcome is a must for every surgeon.

Patient Reported Outcome Measures (PROM), is often used (1) (2).

Outcome scores should be:

- Simple to handle, need a minimum of time, thus being used for almost 100% of patients.
- Possibly applicable in the same way to all anatomic regions.

ICUC Score:

- Describes patient reported data functional limitation and pain, as independent variables.
- Allows to depict postoperative (post treatment) course if used regularly during follow up.
- In contrast to existing scores, the ICUC Score does not go into details, however its repetitive use is very useful for the temporal mapping of improvements or deterioration.

Functional limitation and pain are each graded in 5 levels for present status (on a numerical scale from 0 to 4), including their evolution since last assessment (improving, stable or worsening). Photos that document function such as the range of motion (ROM) supplement independently of subjective grading the evaluation at every stage.

Functional Limitation according to patient	Pain
0 Zero functional limitation. Can do any activity, as before fracture.	0 Zero pain
1 Can do most activities. Some limitations of joint motion. Slight functional impairment.	1 Mild pain
2 Can only do certain activities. Clear limitation of joint motion. Marked functional impairment.	2 Moderate pain
3 Unable to do most activities. Poor range of joint motion.	3 Intense pain
4 Unable to do any activity. Stiff joint.	4 Worst possible pain

 Worsening

A perfect result is: Zero limitations and Zero pain

 Affected limb indicator

Clinical case example:

Fig. 1: Course of ICUC Score in line with course of conventional documentation. Uneventful course, patient reported outcome (pain and functional limitation) and X-ray in line. 65 year-old female patient / [ICUC® ID: Case: 23-VB-925](#)

References:

1. Patient Reported Outcome Measures.
[WWW.AAOS.ORG/QUALITY/PERFORMANCE_MEASURES/
PATIENT_REPORTED_OUTCOME_MEASURES/?SSOPC=1](http://WWW.AAOS.ORG/QUALITY/PERFORMANCE_MEASURES/PATIENT_REPORTED_OUTCOME_MEASURES/?SSOPC=1).
2. E. Nelson et al. Patient Reported Outcome Measures in practice. Published 10 February 2015. BMJ 2015;350:G7818.
3. D. Bennett, B. Hanratty, N. Thompson and D. Beverland: Measurement of knee joint motion using digital imaging. INT ORTHOP. 2009 DEC; 33(6): 1627–1631. DOI: 1007/S00264-008-0694-9.
4. WWW.ICUC.NET